

**RELATIONSHIP OF BLOOD HDL CHOLESTEROL LEVELS IN
OBESITY ASSOCIATED BREAST CANCER**

Mirzayeva M.A.

Tashkent Medical Academy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Breast Cancer is the most common cancer among worldwid women and main cause for women’s died from cancer. High body mass index (BMI) is associated with increased risk of some cancer types According to the WHO classification, a body mass index (BMI) of 25-29.9 kg/m² is overweight, and a BMI \geq 30 kg/m² is considered obesity. 38% of the world's population is overweight and obese[17]. In 2014, 600 million adults worldwide were obese, and 15% of them were women. Recent scientific studies show that overweight and obesity are high risk factors for esophageal adenocarcinoma, stomach, colon, thyroid, ovarian, prostate, myeloma, and breast cancer. Obesity increases the risk of poor prognosis of a number of organ tumor diseases. Obesity causes cancer in approximately 3.5% of men and 9.5% of women. Cancer-related deaths due to obesity are 14.2% and 19.8% in men and women, respectively. In 1402 of 108,812 individuals from the general population developed Breast Cancer during a median of 4.7- years follow-up. In this series of patients, corresponding risk of Breast Cancer was 20% higher in postmenopausal women with high BMI. Considering the relationship between Breast Cancer and obesity; the postulated mechanisms for the increased risk of Breast Cancer in obese women, such as elevated estrogen levels, insulin resistance and the influences of IGF, fatty acids, leptin and adiponectin. In association with oncogenic stimuli, increased plasma cholesterol leads to accelerated tumor formation and increases tumor burden. In mammary tumors increased plasma cholesterol levels are associated with increased expression of cyclin D1, a marker associated with tumor formation, and decreased expression of markers associated with protection. An increase in plasma cholesterol levels accelerates the development of tumors and exacerbates their aggressiveness.

Aim. Analysis of relationship of blood total cholesterol levels in obesity-associated breast cancer.

Materials and methods. This retrospective study was conducted from August 2021 till May 2022 in Tashkent, Republic Specialized Oncology And Radiology Scientific Practice Center We have checked cholesterol levels of the blood, the clinical improvement in obese women, whose have made representation to central polyclinic of Republic Specialized Oncology and Radiology Scientific Practice Center. This study was conducted among obesity associated breast cancer patients (16) in early stage of disease, who taken neoadjuvant chemotherapy as treatment. Youngest patient was 45 and oldest 60 years old, average – 50. Each woman's body mass index was estimated according to WHO criteries. In addition to analyzing the anamnesis associated with metabolic syndrome and cancer, anthropometric parameters were measured in patients, such as body weight, height (to determine body mass index), shoulder and hip joints. To determine the presence of arterial hypertension in patients, blood pressure was determined. ECG and EchoCG studies were performed to determine cardiomyopathy. The amount of glucose in the blood was studied by laboratory tests. Ultrasound and CT analyzes were obtained to assess the effect of chemotherapy.

Results. There were 16 patients with obesity associated breast cancer was involved to the study. 11 out of 16 patients were found to have less than normal HDL cholesterol levels(50mg/dl). Overall, the summary HR for the association between HDLC and breast cancer risk in obese women($p < 0.005$). That is, as the amount of BMI increased, level of HDL cholesterol declined in patients was studied ($p \leq 0.005$).

Conclusion. Obesity carries a 35–40% increased risk of recurrence and death. High

cholesterol levels prior to diagnosis protect against the development of tumors. There is sufficient evidence that obesity and cholesterol impact clinical outcomes. Physicians are advised to take steps to help patients with their weight, such as recommending dietary and lifestyle interventions.

References:

1. Atkinson RL, El-Zein R, Valero V, et al. Epidemiological risk factors associated with inflammatory breast cancer subtypes. *Cancer Causes Control*. 2016;27:359-66..
2. Suzuki R, Orsini N, Saji S, Key TJ, Wolk A. Body weight and incidence of breast cancer defined by estrogen and progesterone receptor status--a meta-analysis. *Int J Cancer*2009;124:698–712. [PubMed: 18988226]
3. Elizabeth R. Berger, Neil M. Iyengar. Obesity and energy balance considerations in triple negative breast cancer. *Cancer journal*.2021; 27(1): 17-24.
4. Angela AndréiaFrançaGravena, Tiara Cristina Romeiro Lopes1, Marcela de Oliveira Demitto, Deise Helena PellosoBorghesan, CátiaMillene Dell’ Agnolo, Sheila Cristina Rocha Brischiliari, Maria Dalva de Barros Carvalho, Sandra Marisa PellosoThe Obesity and the Risk of Breast Cancer among Pre and Postmenopausal Women. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev*, 19 (9), 2429-2436.
5. Marian L. Neuhouser, PhD, RD; Aaron K. Aragaki, MS; Ross L. Prentice, PhD and oth. Overweight, Obesity and Postmenopausal InvasiveBreast Cancer Risk. *JAMA Oncol*. 2015;1(5):611-621.
6. Hursting SD, Digiovanni J, Dannenberg AJ, et al.Obesity, energy balance, and cancer: newopportunities for prevention. *Cancer Prev Res (Phila)*.2012;5(11):1260-1272.